

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

Programme	EU4HEALTH
Project number	101080009
Acronym	CAN.HEAL
Start Date	1 Nov 2022
Duration	30 months

Deliverable information

WP	5
Deliverable related number	5.2
Deliverable number	16
Deliverable name	Inventory of the DSS and recommendations for establishing large scale population-based early intervention programs for the prevention of cancers utilizing NGS and LB
Deliverable Description	Analysis of the augmentation of PRS with LB in case of cancer and recommendations for experimental testing of this approach
Lead Beneficiary	Tartu-UN
Type	R
Dissemination level	PU
Version	1
Due Date	31 December 2024
Delivery Date	30 December 2024
Approval Date	

Deliverable D5.2 - Inventory of the DSS and recommendations for establishing large scale population-based early intervention programs for the prevention of cancers utilizing NGS and LB - Version 1

Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Partner
1.0	30 Dec 2024	First version	Tartu-UN

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Summary

Liquid biopsy emerges as a minimally invasive, cost-effective diagnostic tool that holds great promise for early cancer detection and monitoring. Unlike traditional methods, liquid biopsies utilize biofluid samples such as blood or urine to identify cancer-derived materials like circulating tumour cells and cell-free DNA. These components provide insights into the presence and characteristics of cancers, often before clinical symptoms emerge. Key advantages of liquid biopsy include its ability to detect cancers at early stages, identify multiple cancer types from a single test, and provide information on the tissue of origin. Techniques like next-generation sequencing enhance its precision by analysing genetic and epigenetic markers, while advanced methodologies such as droplet digital PCR and methylation analysis offer high sensitivity and specificity. Challenges such as sample processing standardization, data analysis, and false positives or negatives remain but are areas of active research and innovation.

Liquid biopsies have the potential to revolutionize cancer screening, especially when combined with polygenic risk scores and clinical decision support systems, paving the way for more personalized and timely interventions. Utilizing liquid biopsies strategically for high-risk individuals based on factors like genetic predisposition, family history or lifestyle might be more ethically sound than population-wide screening – it could optimize resource allocation and prioritize those who might benefit most.

Clinical decision support systems have demonstrated their ability to improve patient outcomes across various domains by enhancing preventive care, diagnostic accuracy, prognostic predictions, and treatment decisions. However, challenges remain, including the need for better integration into clinical workflows, addressing data standardization issues, and ensuring user trust in the recommendations provided by these systems. As technology advances, the potential of such systems to revolutionize clinical practice continues to grow.

Objective of the deliverable

Provide recommendations for establishing population-based early intervention programs for the prevention of various cancer types. The deliverable explores the applications of liquid biopsy and decision support systems in enhancing cancer prevention strategies.

There are two main applications of cancer biopsy. The first involves analysing driver mutations in somatic tumour tissue, typically obtained through solid tissue biopsy, to guide diagnosis and treatment decisions. The second approach focuses on analysing germline genomic variants using the polygenic risk score method, which can identify high-risk individuals. This information can then be used to conduct additional testing for early detection of tumour DNA in blood plasma, a method known as liquid biopsy. This review is dedicated to the latter approach.

Deliverable D5.2 - Inventory of the DSS and recommendations for establishing large scale population-based early intervention programs for the prevention of cancers utilizing NGS and LB - Version 1

Work performed

A comprehensive literature review was conducted on two topics: liquid biopsy and decision support systems. In addition to well-known databases such as PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, and Scopus, information was gathered from the websites of national healthcare providers, research institutions, and private companies to capture the current state of knowledge.

Results

Liquid biopsy and polygenic risk scores for early detection of cancers for applications in personalized prevention

Introduction

Cancer is a diverse condition that can originate from essentially all cell types and organs of a human body and has over a hundred distinct entities with diverse risk factors and epidemiologic features (Batool et al., 2023). Despite being one of the leading causes of death worldwide, many cancers do not have screening programs and many people with a high risk of developing cancer fail to follow the advised medical screening regime due to the nature of the available screening tests and other challenges with compliance (Connal et al., 2023). Early detection is key for improved quality of life, survival, and to reduce the financial burden of cancer treatments which are greater at later stage detection. Early signs of cancer can be non-specific and can easily be disregarded by both patients and practitioners since they are not indicative of a specific single organ for further testing.

Most cancers can be classified according to the stage of disease, a measure of how widely it has spread in the primary organ and beyond: stage 0 (i.e., in situ), I, II, III and IV. Cancer stages provide a general understanding of how advanced a cancer is. The staging system considers factors like tumour size, lymph node involvement, and distant metastasis (spread of cancer to other organs). The earliest stage of cancer, often referred to as non-invasive cancer, is stage 0 (carcinoma in situ) where abnormal cells are present but haven't invaded deeper tissues. Stage 0 cancers are typically highly treatable with a good prognosis. Stage I cancer is still localized to its original site and is usually small with minimal lymph node involvement. Stage I cancers generally have a good prognosis with early detection and treatment. Stage II cancer is larger than in Stage I and may have spread to nearby lymph nodes. Prognosis in Stage II varies depending on the specific type and extent of spread. Stage III cancer is more advanced than Stage II and may involve larger tumour size, more extensive lymph node involvement, and tumour spread to surrounding tissues. Stage III cancers typically require more aggressive treatment approaches, and the prognosis can vary significantly depending on the specific factors. Stage IV is the most advanced stage, indicating distant metastasis, where cancer cells have spread to distant organs beyond the original site. Stage IV cancers generally have a poorer prognosis compared to earlier stages. As the tumour stage progresses from I to IV, the growth rate increases and the time period to the next stage decreases (Hubbell et al., 2021), making early detection paramount. In addition, the cost of treating patients diagnosed with stage III/IV cancer is notably increased in comparison to stage I/II cancer (Mariotto et al., 2020).

All cancer is triggered by altered genes and 5-10% of cancers are hereditary (Anand et al., 2008). Studies of twins, families, and unrelated populations have demonstrated substantial heritability and familial clustering for many cancers (Rashkin et al., 2020). Both monogenic and polygenic factors contribute to cancer development.

Monogenic cancers arise from mutations in a single gene, also known as hereditary cancer syndromes. These mutations are often inherited from a parent and significantly increase an individual's risk of developing specific cancers. For example, mutations in the *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* genes are well-known risk factors for breast and ovarian cancer in women,

and some male cancers like prostate cancer. Mutations in genes like *MLH1*, *MSH2*, *MSH6*, *PMS1*, and *PMS2* are associated with an increased risk of colorectal cancer, endometrial cancer, and other cancers. Mutations in the p53 tumour suppressor gene can lead to Li-Fraumeni syndrome, which predisposes individuals to various cancers like breast cancer, sarcoma, and brain tumours. Monogenic cancers often manifest at a younger age compared to sporadic cancers arising from a combination of genetic and environmental factors. A strong family history of specific cancers is a hallmark of monogenic cancers.

Polygenic cancers are caused by the combined effects of variations in multiple genes, each with a small individual impact. These genetic variations do not necessarily follow a clear inheritance pattern and interact with environmental factors to influence cancer risk. Polygenic factors are more commonly associated with widespread cancers like breast cancer, prostate cancer, and colorectal cancer. Lifestyle factors like smoking, diet, and sun exposure significantly influence the overall risk of polygenic cancers.

A **polygenic risk score (PRS)** is a numerical score that reflects an individual's genetic predisposition to a particular trait or disease, based on the combined weighted effect of multiple genetic variants, each of which may have a small effect size on its own. The variant weights used in the calculation are usually derived from large-scale genome-wide association studies (GWAS), where the strength of association between each genetic variant and the trait or disease is estimated. The resulting PRS represents the overall genetic liability for the trait or disease and can be used to identify individuals who are at higher or lower risk among the general population. PRS is typically compared to an average baseline risk within the general population. A higher PRS indicates an increased relative risk for the particular cancer. PRS is not a definitive predictor of whether someone will develop cancer – it provides an estimate of relative risk compared to the average population. Lifestyle choices, diet, and environmental exposures significantly influence cancer risk, and PRS doesn't account for these factors. However, **PRS can help identify individuals with a higher genetic predisposition to cancer, allowing for more targeted screening and prevention strategies. For high-risk individuals, PRS might inform the use of more frequent or intensive screening methods to facilitate earlier cancer detection.** Also, knowing their PRS might motivate individuals to adopt healthier lifestyles, potentially reducing their overall cancer risk. In addition, PRS can be used to identify individuals at high risk for specific cancers, making them suitable candidates for clinical trials of new preventive or therapeutic interventions. PRS alone is not specific enough for clinical intervention in cancers, but **it should be combined with a more precise diagnostic method.**

For most cancer types, symptoms are often unapparent in an early stage, therefore reliable, non-invasive, and cost-effective detection methods are required. Screening for individual cancers is expensive, and it is more efficient to use a multi-cancer test that can detect a range of cancers from a single test. **Liquid biopsy (LB)**, a laboratory test done on a sample of blood, urine, or other body fluid to look for cancer cells from a tumour or small pieces of DNA, RNA, or other molecules released by tumour cells into a person's body fluids, is minimally invasive and has good potential for detecting cancers even at **very early stages**. It also makes possible simultaneous detection of **multiple cancers** by providing the information on the tissue of origin. LB analysis has several advantages over traditional screening methods for early-stage cancers. Abnormal cell-free DNA (cfDNA) can be detected in the plasma at early stages of cancer (1-2 years), before it is possible using

clinical measurements like imaging. There is a general movement in the EU to reduce the overall radiation load in health care.

LB methods for cancer detection

Liquid biopsies involve isolating tiny amounts of tumour-derived materials circulating in blood or other bodily fluids. These materials can provide valuable information for cancer detection, monitoring, and treatment decisions. Isolating and analysing cancer-derived components from liquid biopsies can be challenging due to their rarity amidst a background of healthy cells and nucleic acids. Liquid biopsy involves the study of a sample of a biofluid (blood, cerebrospinal fluid, urine, saliva, amniotic fluid, ascitic fluid), examining cancer-derived circulating tumour cells (CTCs), circulating nucleic acids including cell-free DNA (cfDNA), cell-free RNA including mRNA, long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) and microRNA (miRNA), extracellular vesicles (EVs), tumour-educated platelets, proteins, and metabolites (Batool et al., 2023; Domínguez-Vigil et al., 2018).

Isolation of circulating tumor cells (CTC)

The initial applications of liquid biopsy in the cancer field were focused on CTCs (Charlish, 2016; Connal et al., 2023; Finotti et al., 2018). CTCs are cells shed by tumours into the bloodstream or lymphatic system. When traveling to other areas of the body, CTCs have the potential to cause metastases. CTCs are exceedingly rare, occurring at a frequency of 1 per 10^6 to 10^7 leukocytes (< 10 CTCs per mL of blood) and are challenging to isolate even in patients with metastatic cancer, requiring highly sensitive technologies to efficiently detect and isolate these cells (Batool et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2020). The half-life of CTCs has been reported to be from minutes to several hours (Hanin, 2023).

Isolating CTCs from healthy blood cells is a critical first step in liquid biopsy analysis for cancer. It can be performed using either size-based filtration, immunomagnetic separation or microfluidics. For size-based filtration, filters with precisely sized pores are used. Blood is passed through the filter, allowing healthy blood cells (smaller) to pass through while potentially capturing CTCs (larger) on the filter surface. It is a simple and relatively inexpensive technique and can be enriched for larger CTCs. As a downside, it may not capture all CTCs, particularly smaller ones or those with deformable membranes. It can also trap white blood cells, leading to potential contamination.

For immunomagnetic separation magnetic beads coated with antibodies specific to surface markers present on CTCs are utilized. The blood sample is incubated with these beads, allowing the antibodies to bind to the CTCs. Then, a magnet is used to attract and isolate the bead-CTC complexes from the rest of the blood. It is highly specific for CTCs based on chosen antibody markers and can capture a wider range of CTC sizes compared to size-based filtration. However, it relies on the identification and availability of specific CTC surface markers and may miss CTCs with different marker profiles or those that have lost their markers.

For microfluidics, chips with microchannels and chambers designed for manipulating fluids at the microscale are used. For CTC isolation, these chips can be designed to exploit various physical properties of CTCs. Size-based separation could be used as one option – similar

to filtration, microfluidic channels with specific dimensions can allow healthy cells to pass through while trapping CTCs. Another option is deformability-based isolation – CTCs are often less deformable than healthy blood cells. Microfluidic channels can be designed to identify and isolate CTCs based on their ability to resist deformation as they flow through the chip. The third option is to use dielectrophoresis – this technique uses electrical fields to manipulate and separate cells based on their electrical properties. Microfluidics is a highly versatile platform allowing for design customization based on specific CTC properties. There is potential for label-free isolation and not relying solely on specific markers. It can be integrated with other functionalities like CTC analysis or on-chip processing. The downside is the complexity and expense compared to other techniques.

New approaches to improve CTC isolation efficiency and capture a wider range of CTCs are constantly being developed. These include utilizing combinations of techniques or exploring novel markers and physical properties for CTC identification. For example, microfluidics holds immense promise for the future of CTC isolation due to its versatility and potential for automation. By refining these isolation techniques, scientists aim to maximize the yield and purity of CTCs from liquid biopsies, ultimately leading to the standardization of CTC detection methods, more accurate cancer diagnosis, treatment monitoring, and personalized medicine strategies.

Isolation of cell-free DNA (cfDNA)

Cell-free DNA (cfDNA) is fragmented DNA circulating in biofluids, including fragments released by tumour cells. It is released from cells mainly through apoptosis (programmed cell death), necrosis (accidental cell death) and active secretion from the tumour. Since its discovery, cfDNA has become an appealing biomarker, and the analysis of cfDNA has been utilized in a range of medical technologies, such as prenatal testing, detecting immune diseases, monitoring the effectiveness of an organ transplant, and detecting the presence of cancer (Connal et al., 2023; Yan et al., 2021). Observational studies have determined the half-life of cfDNA in the circulation from minutes to hours (Leung et al., 2016), as a consequence of the action of three main different mechanisms: (i) the action of deoxyribonucleases present in the bloodstream, (ii) the active clearance of nucleosomes and DNA, and (iii) filtration in organs such as kidney or lymph nodes (Sánchez-Herrero et al., 2022).

Circulating tumour DNA (ctDNA) is tumour-derived fragmented DNA in the bloodstream that has come from primary or metastatic cancer sites (Alese et al., 2022). ctDNA has been found to be detectable in >75% of patients with advanced pancreatic, ovarian, colorectal, bladder, gastroesophageal, breast, melanoma, hepatocellular, and head and neck cancers, but in less than 50% of primary brain, renal, prostate, or thyroid cancers (Bettegowda et al., 2014). In patients with localized tumours, Bettegowda et al. (2014) detected ctDNA in 73%, 57%, 48%, and 50% of patients with colorectal cancer, gastroesophageal cancer, pancreatic cancer, and breast adenocarcinoma, respectively. ctDNA half-life ranges from 15 min to about 2.5 h (Caputo et al., 2023).

The concentration of ctDNA increases with the stage and tumour size (Chen and Zhao, 2019) but still, ctDNA levels are generally rather low. In people with cancer this accounts for around 1% to 2% of the overall cfDNA (Wyatt et al., 2017), ranging from ≥ 5 –10% in late stage

to ≤ 0.01 – 0.1% in early-stage cancers or early post-surgical tumour recurrence (Bettegowda et al., 2014). The size of the cfDNA varies, with a length ranging from 18 bp to 10,000 bp (Zhang et al., 2019). Intriguingly, tumour-derived DNA fragments appear to be smaller – approximately 143 to 145 bp (compatible with the size of a mononucleosome without a linker) – than the normal cfDNA fragment-size distribution, which displays a peak around 166 bp (the size of DNA on a mononucleosome with a linker) (Alese et al., 2022).

ctDNA can be distinguished from normal cfDNA fragments through the presence of epigenetic or genetic alterations including tumour-specific methylation markers and somatic mutations (Ramirez-Garrastacho et al., 2022). Techniques like size-based isolation (centrifugation or precipitation) or targeted capture using specific probes used to capture cfDNA fragments containing mutations or other features associated with cancer are used to isolate cfDNA from total blood DNA. ctDNA is used to study tumour-specific mutations, CNVs, methylation changes, or integrated viral sequences (Nassiri et al., 2020).

ctDNA analysis methods

In the context of ctDNA liquid biopsy, many different technologies and panel tests have been developed to analyse the molecular alterations for different purposes: polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based sequencing can be used for single-locus/multiplexed assays and targeted sequencing for point mutations analysis, next generation sequencing (NGS) can be used for single-locus/multiplexed assays, targeted sequencing, genome-wide analysis for point mutations, detection of rearrangements, chromosomal copy-number changes, and whole genome analysis (Caputo et al., 2023). When determining the most suitable method of analysis, one needs to consider the clinical application of ctDNA detection, as each has different characteristics in terms of assay sensitivity, loci coverage, cost, and turnaround time (Alese et al., 2022).

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) is a fundamental laboratory technique widely used in molecular biology and various other fields. PCR can rapidly make millions to billions of copies (amplifications) of a specific DNA segment. This technique is crucial because many biological studies require a large amount of DNA for analysis, and often, the starting sample might be very limited.

Real-time PCR, also sometimes called quantitative PCR (qPCR), is a variation of the standard PCR technique that allows for monitoring the amplification of a target DNA molecule as the reaction progresses, in "real time" rather than at the end. This provides a continuous picture of how the target DNA is increasing throughout the PCR process. Traditional PCR only allows quantification at the end point. Real-time PCR can also be used to quantify the starting amount of target DNA present in the sample. This is achieved by comparing the fluorescence signal at each cycle to a standard curve generated using known amounts of target DNA. Traditional PCR is qualitative (presence or absence) or semi-quantitative (rough estimate of amount). qPCR can detect mutant allele fractions and it is efficient when it analyses a small number of variants, but it can assess only specified variant types, thus offering little discovery value (Olmedillas-López et al., 2022).

The digital PCR (dPCR) is like qPCR in principle, but it is superior to qPCR in accuracy – it divides the sample into thousands of parallel PCR reactions, so the background noise is reduced (Caputo et al., 2023). The most widely used platform at this time is a type of dPCR

called droplet digital PCR (ddPCR), which provides absolute quantitative analysis and has the ability to detect variants with a mutated allele fraction as low as a 0.01%, making it the ideal tool for monitoring postoperative minimal residual disease, as long as the mutations have already been identified in an individual's tumour tissue (Alese et al., 2022). However, the utility of droplet digital PCR is generally restricted to single genomic lesions, such as point mutations or small indels (Alese et al., 2022).

To overcome the limitations of PCR-based techniques, advances in next generation sequencing technologies can provide information on the entire genome or specific gene panels, allowing for the detection of even very low levels of ctDNA in the blood and detection of different types of alterations (e.g., point mutations, insertions, deletions, gene fusions and translocations) (Brockley et al., 2023). NGS is characterized by different steps: generation of a fragment DNA library, single fragment clonal amplification, massive parallel ultra-deep sequencing of millions of different DNA fragments, followed by computational analysis of reads (Caputo et al., 2023). NGS can be used to discover new molecular alterations without prior knowledge at the end of the test, offering a higher discovery value (Chen et al., 2019).

A NGS technique entailing sequencing the exome or protein-coding portions of the genome is called whole exome sequencing (WES). It covers approximately 1-2% of the genome, but this region harbours most known disease-causing mutations. It provides for a thorough examination of coding mutations across hundreds of genes and makes it possible to detect both well-known and undiscovered genetic changes in liquid biopsy samples (Shegekar et al., 2023). WES is ideal for identifying mutations in known cancer genes, making it suitable for targeted analysis when specific mutations are suspected based on tumour type or other clinical information. For covering the entire DNA sequence of an organism including both the exome and the non-coding regions (introns, regulatory elements), whole genome sequencing (WGS) is used. WGS provides a broader view of the genome, potentially revealing unknown mutations, gene fusions, and other genetic alterations not limited to known cancer genes. WGS is valuable for research purposes to identify novel cancer driver mutations and understand the complex interplay of genetics in cancer development. However, WGS is more expensive than WES and the analysis takes longer and more computational resources. If there's a strong suspicion of mutations in specific genes, WES might be sufficient. For a more comprehensive analysis or research purposes, WGS might be preferred.

Most clinical ctDNA assays focus on genomic alterations, limiting their ability to detect clinically important features of cancer that are measured from tumour tissues, such as histologic subtypes and expression of key genes (Baca et al., 2023). To overcome the limitations of traditional mutation and fragmentation-based liquid biopsy testing, the use of cancer-specific methylation signals is being explored (Kwon et al., 2023). Methylation analysis focuses on identifying abnormal patterns of DNA methylation, a natural chemical modification that plays a crucial role in gene regulation. 5-methylcytosine (5-mC) is the predominant epigenetic mark in mammalian genomic DNA. 5-hydroxymethylcytosine (5-hmC) is a newly discovered epigenetic modification that is presumably generated by oxidation of 5-methylcytosine by the TET (ten-eleven translocation) family of cytosine oxygenases. 5-methylcytosine (5mC) is associated with gene repression, while 5-hydroxymethylcytosine (5hmC) is thought to represent a transition state towards the removal of gene repression (meaning active or bivalent states). In healthy cells, DNA

methylation acts like an on/off switch for genes. Methylation typically silences genes, while demethylation allows for gene expression.

Cancer cells often exhibit abnormal methylation patterns. Genes that should be turned on (tumour suppressors) might be silenced through hypermethylation, while oncogenes (cancer-promoting genes) might be inappropriately activated due to demethylation. ctDNA methylation analysis is not an addition to NGS analysis, but rather one application of NGS technology. NGS platforms can be used for targeted sequencing, where focus can be directed on specific regions of the genome relevant for methylation analysis. While NGS is a common platform for ctDNA methylation analysis, other techniques like methylation-specific PCR can also be used. However, NGS offers advantages in terms of broader coverage, higher sensitivity, and the ability to analyse multiple methylation markers simultaneously.

Bisulfite sequencing has been the gold standard method for DNA methylation analysis for a long time, but long-read sequencing technologies are emerging as a potential alternative. Bisulfite sequencing is a mature and widely used technique with well-defined protocols and extensive research data available. It is generally less expensive compared to long-read sequencing and can detect methylation even at low levels. However, bisulfite sequencing generates short reads, which can limit the ability to analyse methylation patterns across long distances or repetitive regions. Bisulfite treatment process can damage DNA, potentially affecting the accuracy of methylation analysis. Also, traditional bisulfite sequencing cannot differentiate between 5-methylcytosine (5mC) and 5-hydroxymethylcytosine (5hmC), which can be important for some studies. Long-read sequencing technologies can read entire DNA molecules, enabling analysis of methylation patterns across large genomic regions. Some long-read sequencing methods minimize DNA damage compared to bisulfite treatment. Certain long-read sequencing techniques can directly differentiate between 5mC and 5hmC, providing more detailed information.

Long-read sequencing technologies coupled with downstream data analysis methods are under active development with new implementations being released on a yearly basis.

Isolation of circulating tumor RNA (ctRNA)

Cell-free RNA (cfRNA) are RNA fragments which are degraded and released into the bloodstream mainly by necrotic or apoptotic cells (Martinez-Dominguez et al., 2021). Circulating tumour RNA (ctRNA) refers to the fraction of circulating cell-free RNA derived from cancer cells. ctRNA is an emerging biomarker that could provide unique information not found in CTCs and ctDNA (Stejskal et al., 2023). Compared to healthy individuals, cancer patients' blood has been observed to contain increased levels of messenger RNA (mRNA) and non-coding RNA (ncRNA) (Anfossi et al., 2018; Cheng et al., 2009). RNA in comparison to DNA is regarded as an unstable molecule with a half-life in plasma of approximately only 15 s (De Rubis et al., 2019). This lack of stability is one of the major limitations associated with ctRNAs, and an optimal extraction method has yet to be identified (Connal et al., 2023).

The research surrounding non-coding RNA (ncRNA) has increased particularly in small RNAs for potential use as prognostic and diagnostic disease biomarkers, due to their higher stability and abundance (Connal et al., 2023). MicroRNA (miRNA) has gained the

most interest due to its stability, moreover in most human cancers the miRNA levels are altered, its expression is tissue specific, and it can be detected not only in tissue samples but also in serum and urine (Connal et al., 2023). When using miRNA detection in the diagnosis of haematological cancer, the pooled specificity was determined to be 85% with a sensitivity of 81% (Drokow et al., 2019).

Isolation of extracellular vesicles (EVs)

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are small membranous structures (microvesicles, exosomes, ectosomes, oncosomes) generally 30–120 nm in diameter, released from the cells, including tumour cells, and contain nucleic acids (DNA, mRNA, miRNA, non-coding RNA), proteins, lipids, or other metabolites with the enclosed cargo closely reflecting the cell of origin (Batool et al., 2023). Each cancer cell type secretes a specific EV, allowing it to determinate the presence of the cancer and the cancer type (Tamura et al., 2021). The disease-specific cargo, long half-life, and physical stability in collected biofluids advocates for their role as promising diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers for multiple diseases including cancer (Batool et al., 2023). However, the lack of unified adequate isolation methods and standardized analysis is a great limitation of EV implementation in the clinical setting (Caputo et al., 2023).

Identifying tissue of origin

Genomic changes, epigenetic markers, and fragment size can be used to detect the presence of ctDNA in the circulation and to infer also the tissue of origin (Alese et al., 2022). Current technology allows us to identify close to 50 different tissues where cancer originates. Dead cells release DNA fragments into the circulation, and some DNA fragments carry information that indicates their tissues-of-origin (TOOs). Based on the signals used for identifying the TOOs of cfDNAs, the existing methods can be classified into three categories: cfDNA mutation-based methods, cfDNA fragmentation pattern-based methods and methylation pattern-based methods.

In cfDNA mutation-based methods, distinct single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) or genetic mutations can indicate the TOOs of cfDNAs. Once the distinct SNPs or causal mutations of a disease have been revealed, PCR-based techniques and sequencing methods are commonly used for detecting mutations in cfDNAs (Peng et al., 2021). cfDNA mutations can be extracted from both targeted sequencing and whole genome sequencing data. In non-invasive cancer screening, assays are usually developed to screen for one certain disease by detecting mutations in cfDNAs associated with disease-related genes (Peng et al., 2021). Although significant differences can be observed between the detected mutations in patients and healthy individuals, the TOOs of tumour-derived cfDNAs and the location of a disease cannot be accurately identified based on the detected mutations since some driven genes are shared by more than one cancer, and the number of gene mutations is limited (Peng et al., 2021). To call reliable mutations in cfDNAs, a matched cfDNA-white blood cell sequencing should be required to exclude false positives from white blood cells, since the source of a large proportion of cfDNA mutations is from clonal haematopoiesis mutations (Razavi et al., 2019).

The cfDNA fragmentation is not a random process – the fragmentation patterns of cfDNAs, including the nucleosome positioning of different cell types, tissue-preferred ends and the length distribution of cfDNA, may indicate their TOOs (Peng et al., 2021). However, the results so far show that these cfDNA fragmentation patterns have limited power to indicate the TOOs of cfDNAs and estimate the corresponding fractions in other samples (Peng et al., 2021).

DNA methylation is a type of epigenetic modification that adds a covalent methyl group at cytosine residues, especially in CpG dinucleotides (Peng et al., 2021). Different tissues or cell types, including the normal and aberrant ones, have different DNA methylation patterns. DNA methylation can be a good indicator of the TOOs of cfDNAs since different tissues and cell types have different methylated patterns (Kundaje et al., 2015). Diseased tissues also have their own distinct DNA methylation profiles like gain of CpG methylation in CpG-enriched promoters and a loss of CpG methylation in non-CpG island promoters (Fernandez et al., 2012). The DNA methylation modifications on cytosine residues are not erased when cfDNAs are released from dead cells so the tissue-specific methylation patterns can be used to indicate the TOOs of cfDNAs (Peng et al., 2021). The performance of methylation pattern-based methods indicates that methylation markers have a strong signal intensity for indicating the TOOs of cfDNAs and can be used to estimate the tissue-derived fractions of cfDNAs (Peng et al., 2021). Methylation markers have a better abundance and medium signal intensity than the other two types of signals for indicating the tissues-of-origin of cfDNAs (Peng et al., 2021). The methylation pattern-based methods are very promising and have great potential in non-invasive diagnostics.

Data analysis

Interpreting the complex data generated from liquid biopsies, especially NGS analysis of cfDNA, requires expertise and ongoing research to understand the significance of specific mutations and their association with cancer risk or aggressiveness. NGS generates a vast amount of data that requires robust computational tools and expertise for analysis.

For pre-processing, the raw sequencing data from NGS platforms needs quality control checks to ensure accuracy and remove artifacts or errors introduced during the sequencing process. The sequenced reads (short DNA fragments) need to be aligned to a reference genome to determine their precise location. Variant calling identifies genetic variations like mutations, insertions, deletions, and copy number alterations within the ctDNA compared to the reference genome. For methylation analysis, specific software is used to calculate methylation levels at different regions of the genome based on sequencing reads.

Downstream analysis includes variant prioritization, tumour burden estimation, and machine learning. Not all identified variants are relevant for cancer. Bioinformatics tools are used to prioritize variants likely to be associated with cancer development based on factors like variant type, location within known cancer genes, and presence in cancer databases. The amount of ctDNA present in the sample (tumour burden) can be estimated by analysing the proportion of reads harbouring cancer-associated variants. Higher tumour burden might indicate advanced or aggressive cancer. Machine learning algorithms are increasingly used to integrate various data points like mutation profiles, methylation patterns, and clinical information to improve the accuracy of cancer detection and predict disease course.

The results of data analysis are then integrated with the patient's clinical history, symptoms, and other diagnostic tests to arrive at a comprehensive picture. The data analysis findings are presented in a way that aids healthcare professionals in making informed decisions about diagnosis, treatment planning, and patient prognosis. This might involve risk stratification for further testing or guiding personalized treatment strategies. Data analysis for liquid biopsies in early cancer detection is a rapidly evolving field. By employing advanced computational tools, machine learning, and integrating various data sources, researchers are working towards improving the sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy of liquid biopsies for early cancer diagnosis and personalized medicine approaches.

Challenges and considerations

Sample collection and processing

The effectiveness of liquid biopsy analysis depends on using the proper sample collecting and processing procedures – appropriate collection procedures, including standardized protocols for blood draws or urine collection, guarantee the preservation and stability of biomarkers during sample processing (Shegekar et al., 2023). For example, ctDNA levels may be affected by systemic and local treatments, such as chemotherapy, targeted therapy, immunotherapy, or radiotherapy, and by other concurrent inflammatory processes or trauma (e.g., infection or surgery) (Alese et al., 2022). Early-stage cancers shed lower amounts of ctDNA, making detection of mutations and methylation changes more challenging.

Clinical validation and utility

Assessing the performance of the specific technology used for the liquid biopsy and the assay itself involves evaluating factors like limit of detection (the minimum amount of target analyte that can be reliably detected by the assay), limit of quantification (the lowest concentration of the analyte that can be measured with acceptable accuracy and precision), specificity (the ability of the assay to distinguish the target analyte from other background noise or similar molecules), sensitivity (the ability of a test to correctly classify an individual as affected) and reproducibility (ensuring the assay produces consistent results across different runs and instruments).

For clinical validation, data from patients with confirmed cancer needs to be compared to data from healthy controls without cancer. This helps establish the assay's ability to differentiate between diseased and healthy states. Following a group of individuals over time, some with high cancer risk and some with low risk and monitoring who develops cancer and how the liquid biopsy results correlate with disease development provides insights into the assay's sensitivity and specificity for early cancer detection. Comparing the performance of the liquid biopsy analysis with established diagnostic methods like tissue biopsies helps to assess the assay's effectiveness in identifying cancer compared to current gold standards.

Implementing robust data quality control measures ensures the integrity and accuracy of the data generated from liquid biopsies. This includes standardization of procedures, inclusion of positive and negative controls, and data normalization. The latter accounts for technical variations and ensures that data is comparable across samples. Ensuring the

studies have sufficient sample size to provide statistically significant results improves statistical power. Data analysis methods need to be rigorously validated in clinical trials to ensure their accuracy and effectiveness for early cancer detection in liquid biopsies. The utility of liquid biopsy tests for early cancer detection can be demonstrated through studies indicating an increased detection rate of early-stage cancers and a higher true detection rate when utilizing liquid biopsies. Showing that using liquid biopsies leads to better patient outcomes, such as increased survival rates or earlier treatment initiation, will ultimately prove the utility of the proposed approach. Liquid biopsies need to be integrated seamlessly into existing diagnostic workflows for improved patient care and earlier intervention.

Sensitivity and specificity

Sensitivity of a test refers to the ability to correctly identify individuals who truly have the disease or condition being tested for. A high sensitivity test means very few true positives (people with the disease) are missed by the test. Specificity is a test's ability to correctly identify individuals who do not have the disease. A high specificity test means very few false positives (people without the disease who test positive) are identified (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The basis for deriving sensitivity, specificity, and false positive and false negative rates.

A screening test for cancer must have high sensitivity for early-stage disease, for which intervention is more likely to lead to cure than for late-stage cancers (Turnbull et al., 2024). Liquid biopsies can be challenging for early-stage cancers as the amount of tumour-derived material in blood (CTCs and cfDNA) might be very low. In comparison to tissue biopsies, liquid biopsies are generally less sensitive and specific, which can lead to an increase in the occurrence of false positives (identifying healthy cells as cancerous) and false negatives (missed cancers) (Lone, 2022; Martins et al., 2021).

High false negative rate of ctDNA assays points to the need for further technological advancements to support liquid biopsy standardization and improve test performance (Alix-Panabieres and Pantel, 2021). False negative results (e.g., undetectable ctDNA or variants of interest when they are actually present in the tumour) may be related to low plasma volume, low ctDNA levels that prevent detection of the variant, low-shedding tumour types, types of variants or anatomic sites known to be associated with low ctDNA levels (e.g., peritoneum), vascularization or histology of the cancer lesions (such as the

isolated brain metastasis), absence of specific molecular alterations in the panel used, and rare allelic frequencies and variants that limit the assay's ability to detect mutations (Alese et al., 2022; Caputo et al., 2023). Molecular confirmation of the presence of high levels of ctDNA in another somatic mutation, or the use of an orthogonal approach such as DNA methylation and fragment analysis, may help distinguish a true-negative result from a false negative (noninformative) result (Alese et al., 2022).

The false positive rate is also important, since it governs the volume of downstream tests required, which are typically expensive and invasive (Turnbull et al., 2024). False positive ctDNA results may occur because of a sequencing error or the presence of nontumor-derived variants (Alese et al., 2022).

Standardization

Standardization of techniques for isolating and analysing liquid biopsy components across different laboratories is essential for reliable and comparable results. This includes ensuring consistent protocols, reagents, and data analysis procedures. Also, standardizing data analysis pipelines and interpretation across laboratories is crucial for reliable and comparable results.

The International Liquid Biopsy Standardization Alliance (ILSA) comprises organizations and foundations that recognize the importance of working towards the global use of liquid biopsy in oncology practice to support clinical decision making and regulatory considerations and seek to promote it in their communities (Connors et al., 2020). ILSA alongside with the European Liquid Biopsy Society (ELBS), CancerID, Standardization of generic Pre-analytical procedures for In-vitro DIAgnostics for Personalized Medicine (SPIDIA), and BLOODPAC have collaborated to establish standards in liquid biopsy pre-analytical phase provided by the International Standards Organisation (ISO) and Technical Specifications from the European Committee for Standardization (CEN/TS). In particular, ISO 20186-3:2019 constitutes a standard for isolation of circulating cell-free DNA from plasma, while CEN/TS 17390-3:2020 focuses on specifications for analytical staining of CTCs. These standards encompass the entire workflow, including documentation, blood sample collection, processing and storage of samples in a controlled environment. Despite their undeniable importance, widespread implementation of these standards remains limited – only few recent scientific papers dealing with liquid biopsies mention the implementation of these standards (Bonstingl et al., 2023). Following the ISO and CEN/TS standards and ensuring thorough documentation, pre-analytical errors, such as missing tube inversion, prolonged times of sample processing, or unknown exposure to temperature variations have been demonstrated to be effectively eliminated (Bonstingl et al., 2023).

Cost-effectiveness

Liquid biopsy tests can be expensive, and their cost-effectiveness for widespread use as a screening tool still needs to be carefully evaluated as there are only a few studies exploring the cost-effectiveness of liquid biopsy tests in cancer screening. This includes considering the potential benefits and costs of additional diagnostic procedures triggered by positive test results.

Fagery et al. (2023) did a systematic review of 24 studies on the cost-effectiveness of liquid biopsy technologies across different cancer types and stages. They found that liquid

biopsies could provide a cost-effective approach for treatment selection in lung cancer and aid in the screening and early detection of other cancers, including colorectal, gastric, breast, and brain cancers. For brain cancer, spectroscopic liquid biopsy has been shown to be cost effective in both primary and secondary care settings with the cost-consequence analysis demonstrating additional utility and cost savings from providing tumour-type classification probabilities (Gray et al., 2021). But again, the price of the test remains a critical factor. For colorectal cancer, it has been demonstrated that offering liquid biopsy testing to patients who refuse colonoscopy results in the greatest gain of life-years but is, however, not cost-effective (Aziz et al., 2023). Liquid biopsy tests for CRC screening may become cost-effective only in the future if they are significantly less expensive. There are large differences in treatment costs for colorectal cancer between countries. Even small improvements in the progression of cancer and the survival of cancer patients could lead to the economic efficiency of liquid biopsy for the health care system (Schramm et al., 2024).

As technology advances and the cost of liquid biopsies decreases, they might become more cost-effective for broader applications in early cancer detection. Additionally, ongoing research is focusing on improving their accuracy and incorporating them into risk-stratification strategies for more targeted screening approaches.

Ethical considerations

Firstly, main concerns regarding using LB for cancer screening stem from false negative and false positive results. False negatives, where a liquid biopsy fails to detect cancer despite its presence, can lead to delayed diagnosis, progression of the disease, and worse patient outcomes. A negative liquid biopsy result might provide a false sense of security, leading patients to delay seeking further medical attention if symptoms persist. False positive results, where a liquid biopsy indicates cancer when none is present, pose another set of ethical dilemmas in early cancer detection.

A false positive can lead to unnecessary and potentially risky invasive procedures like biopsies or imaging tests to confirm or rule out cancer. The psychological stress and anxiety of a potential cancer diagnosis, even if later deemed false, can be significant. In some cases, a false positive might lead to diagnosing and treating a cancer that wouldn't have progressed or posed a threat. This can subject patients to unnecessary treatment with potential side effects. Investigating and managing false positives can strain healthcare resources, diverting attention and resources away from patients with genuine cancer diagnoses. Frequent false positives or negatives can erode public trust in liquid biopsies and cancer screening programs in general.

Healthcare professionals need to be transparent with patients about the limitations of liquid biopsies, including the possibility of false negatives and positives. Discussing the possibility of false negatives and positives during pretest counselling helps patients understand the limitations of the test and make informed decisions. Patients should be involved in shared decision-making with their healthcare providers when considering liquid biopsies, weighing the potential benefits and risks based on individual circumstances. Psychological support and clear communication about the limitations of these tests are crucial.

Currently, some liquid biopsies can be expensive, potentially limiting access for low-income patients. Ensuring equitable access to this technology is important. Supporting

research aimed at developing more cost-effective liquid biopsy technologies can make them more accessible. In addition, governments and healthcare systems can negotiate with test manufacturers to reduce costs and establish fair pricing structures. Also, including liquid biopsies within the scope of public or private health insurance can significantly improve access for low-income individuals. Collaboration between governments, healthcare providers, pharmaceutical companies, and patient advocacy groups is crucial to develop and implement effective strategies for ensuring equitable access.

Using liquid biopsies with high accuracy and focusing on high-risk individuals can help minimize the risk of false positives. Utilizing liquid biopsies strategically for high-risk individuals based on factors like genetic predisposition, family history or lifestyle might be more ethically sound than population-wide screening – it could optimize resource allocation and prioritize those who might benefit most.

Continuous research is crucial to improve the accuracy of liquid biopsies and minimize false results. As liquid biopsy tests evolve, clear regulations and oversight are needed to ensure their accuracy, validity, and appropriate clinical use. Using liquid biopsies for early cancer detection presents a complex ethical landscape. Clear guidelines should be established for how to manage a positive liquid biopsy result, including appropriate confirmatory tests to minimize unnecessary procedures. Open communication, patient education, and ongoing research are essential to ensure this technology is used responsibly and ethically.

Overview of LB test kits currently on the market (non-exhaustive)

CTC detection liquid biopsy tests

- CELLSEARCH® Circulating Tumor Cell Kit (Menarini Silicon Biosystems, Italy and USA). The presence of CTCs in the peripheral blood detected by the CELLSEARCH® CTC Test is associated with decreased progression-free survival and decreased overall survival in patients treated for metastatic breast, colorectal, or prostate cancer. It is intended for the enumeration of CTCs of epithelial origin (CD45-, EpCAM+, and cytokeratins 8, 18+, and/or 19+) in whole blood. Evaluation of CTCs at any time during the course of disease allows assessment of patient prognosis and is predictive of progression-free survival and overall survival. CELLSEARCH® CTC Test results should be used in conjunction with all clinical information derived from diagnostic tests (e.g., imaging, laboratory tests), physical examination, and complete medical history, in accordance with appropriate management procedures (CellSearch, 2024). CELLSEARCH® CTC Test is FDA approved.

ctDNA detection liquid biopsy tests utilizing spectroscopy

- Dxcover® Cancer Liquid Biopsy (Dxcover Limited, UK) – the ATR-FTIR spectroscopic liquid biopsy utilizes an inclusive signal analysis which allows the interrogation of a wide range of molecules such as lipids, carbohydrates, proteins, electrolytes and metabolites. This generates a spectral signature that captures the full range of potential markers contained in human blood serum, combining both tumour- and immune-derived information. In a study by Cameron et al. (2023) the ability of the platform to differentiate between non-cancer patients and various cancer types was determined:

brain, breast, colorectal, kidney, lung, ovarian, pancreatic, and prostate cancer. With a sensitivity-tuned model, focused on cancer versus asymptomatic non-cancer patients akin to screening an asymptomatic population, sensitivity was 98% and specificity of 58%. Alternatively, the specificity-tuned model had sensitivity of 56% and specificity of 99%. The key result for this study however lies in the ability to detect early-stage cancers (I and II) due to the analysis across biomolecular classes that originate from the tumour and from the immune response rather than just focusing on tumour related information (Connal et al., 2023).

- Nodify xl2 (Biodesix, USA) – lung cancer detection, measures proteins from blood with liquid chromatography (mass spectrometry).

ctDNA detection liquid biopsy tests identifying DNA mutations

- Guardant360® CDx (Guardant Health, USA) – a next-generation sequencing (NGS) liquid biopsy test that analyses ctDNA from blood samples. Guardant360® detects somatic variants in a targeted panel of 74 genes and high microsatellite instability (MSI-High). It detects genetic alterations such as point mutations, insertions, deletions, and copy number variations across a panel of genes associated with various cancer types (Cui et al., 2022; Guardant Health, Inc, 2024). FDA approved. It is also commercially available in Europe and has received CE-IVD (Conformité Européenne – In Vitro Diagnostic) marking.
- FoundationOne® Liquid CDx (Foundation Medicine, USA) – designed to detect several mutations in cfDNA in several types of cancer. It identifies genomic alterations including substitutions, insertions, deletions, and copy number alterations in over 300 cancer-related genes. This test also reports blood tumour mutational burden (bTMB), microsatellite instability high (MSI-H), and tumour fraction values. FDA approved.
- Cobas® EGFR Mutation Test v2 (Roche, Switzerland) – detects mutations in the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) gene using real-time PCR (polymerase chain reaction) technology. It specifically detects mutations in exons 18, 19, 20, and 21 of the EGFR gene, which are commonly associated with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). FDA approved.
- Plasma-SeqSensei™ Breast Cancer IVD Kit (Sysmex Europe SE, Germany) – in vitro diagnostic (CE-IVD marked) kit for detecting mutations in cfDNA associated with breast cancer. The kit covers key gene mutations from AKT1, ERBB2, ESR1, KRAS, PIK3CA and TP53 to detect established and emerging predictive markers, resistance mutations and frequently occurring genetic alterations in breast cancer (Sysmex Europe, 2024). Not FDA approved, for research purposes.

ctDNA detection liquid biopsy tests identifying DNA methylation

- Epi proColon (Epigenomics AG, Germany) – a blood-based test for colorectal cancer screening that detects methylated Septin9 DNA using PCR-based technology. FDA approved.

- **GRAIL Galleri (Grail Bio, an Illumina spinoff, USA)** – a multi-cancer screening test for people over the age of 50. It is based on cell-free DNA and detects tumour-specific methylation patterns by bisulfite sequencing to predict the tissue of origin. It can use the signal to potentially screen for more than 50 cancer types originating in multiple organ systems (kidney, lung, adrenal glands, gastrointestinal tract, oral cavity, etc.). In its current incarnation, the Galleri multiple cancer early detection (MCED) test has shown overall sensitivity of only 27.5% for early-stage cancer (stage I-II) (Klein et al., 2021). This figure is based on performance in patients with symptomatic disease and is likely to overestimate the screening performance. The test sensitivity was improved to 52.8% by restricting analysis to a set of 12 cancers the Galleri authors specified as being of high unmet need (Turnbull et al., 2024). The false-positive rate of the Galleri-MCED test is claimed to be 0.5% (Klein et al., 2021). Ongoing studies to determine the performance of the Galleri test include NHS-Galleri trial and the PATHFINDER study. Breakthrough Device designation from the FDA, not full approval.
- **Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT, UK)** allows for sequencing up to 100 kb stretches of genomic DNA without PCR and this enables direct detection of intact methylation alongside nucleotide sequence without chemical conversion or additional library preparation steps. Since the methylation pattern is tissue-specific, analysing the cfDNA allows establishing cancer tissue of origin, compared to the normal, noncancerous cfDNA. ONT has developed the Reduced-Representation Methylation Sequencing (RRMS) method for methylation testing and necessary software to analyse the results. ONT technology is suited not only for analysing the conventional 5mC, but also 5hmC (5-hydroxy methyl C).
- **Guardant Infinity (Guardant Health, USA)** detects an aggregated methylation signal that can distinguish cancer patients from cancer-free patients, at 91% sensitivity and 97% specificity across a cohort of lung, breast, and CRC samples (Guardant Health generated data). Not FDA approved, used for research purposes only.
- **Illumina Infinium MethylationEPIC BeadChip Kits (Illumina, USA)** utilizes methylation profiling technology. It can analyse methylation patterns across the genome from various sample types, including cfDNA. Not FDA approved, used for research purposes only.

ctDNA detection liquid biopsy tests utilizing a multimodal approach

- **CancerSEEK (Exact Sciences, USA)** combines assays for genetic alterations and protein biomarkers for the early detection of cancer. CancerSEEK was used in a study of patients (n = 1005) that had been diagnosed with stage I-III cancers, examining eight cancer types (ovary, liver, stomach, pancreas, esophagus, colorectum, lung or breast). The test gave a specificity of > 99% with sensitivities of 43%, 73% and 78% for stages I, II and III respectively (Cohen et al., 2018). These results are encouraging, but still over half of stage I cancers would be missed (Connal et al., 2023). FDA approved.
- **Cologuard (Exact Sciences, USA)** – stool-based DNA and blood screening test for CRC. Cologuard doesn't directly detect DNA sequences that code for specific genes. Instead, it uses a multi-marker approach that analyses stool samples for specific point

mutations in the *KRAS* gene, methylation patterns of *NDRG4* and *BMP3*, blood in stool (faecal haemoglobin), and total human DNA as a reference point to ensure an adequate amount of sample was analysed. Sensitivity and specificity of 87% and sensitivity of 92% (Choi and Kim, 2022). FDA approved.

- Shield™ (Guardant Health, USA) – a qualitative blood test, intended to detect colorectal neoplasia through identifying genomic and epigenomic alterations in cfDNA, and proteomic changes in plasma from blood collected in guardant blood collection tubes. Integrates genomics, epigenomics and proteomics, to achieve high sensitivity and specificity in detecting early signs of colorectal cancer in average-risk adults age 45 and older. 90% specificity, 83% sensitivity, 99.9% negative predictive value (Chung et al., 2024). Pending FDA approval.
- PacBio Revio (Pacific Biosciences, USA) – single molecule, real time (SMRT) sequencing, empowers HiFi sequencing (highly accurate long sequencing reads). SMRT sequencing technology entails immobilizing the DNA polymerase at the bottom of tiny wells known as zero-mode waveguides. Fluorescently labelled nucleotides are then added, and as the DNA polymerase incorporates them into the growing strand, the emitted light is detected and used to determine the DNA sequence. With a high-density, 25 million ZMW SMRT Cell, up to 4 SMRT Cells in parallel, and 24-hour run times, the Revio system delivers 360 Gb of HiFi reads per day, equivalent to 1,300 human whole genomes per year. HiFi sequencing provides small variants, structural variants, repeat expansions, methylation, and haplotype phasing from a single library and sequencing run. The Revio system includes powerful NVIDIA GPUs to deliver accurate, ready-to-use data directly from the instrument. The GPUs provide rapid turnaround time for base calling and HiFi read generation, directly outputting HiFi reads in BAM format. DeepConsensus uses advanced deep learning techniques to further extend the accuracy and yield of HiFi sequencing. Standard runs include DNA methylation status, calculated with a deep learning algorithm that processes polymerase kinetics. All fundamental processing steps are performed on instrument (Pacific Biosciences, 2024). Not FDA approved, for research purposes.

ctRNA detection liquid biopsy tests

- SelectMDx (MDx Health, Belgium) – a non-invasive urine liquid biopsy which measures the expression of two mRNA cancer-related biomarkers and combines this information with clinical risk factors to stratify patients for clinically significant prostate cancer. These results can help the physician determine if a patient can avoid a biopsy and return to routine screening, or if the patient may benefit from a biopsy for prostate cancer detection. From a validation cohort consisting of 715 patients with serum PSA less than 10 ng/mL, an AUC of 0.82 was achieved with a sensitivity of 89%, specificity of 53% and an NPV of 95% (Haese et al., 2019).
- COLOX™ (Novigenix, Switzerland) – designed for detection of pre-cancerous lesions (advanced adenomas) and early-stage colorectal cancer. It is a RNA-based biomarker test that measures the immune system reaction to the onset of colorectal cancer (CRC). The test analyses the transcriptome of the peripheral blood mononuclear cells

(PBMC's) from a blood sample drawn in routine medical practice. COLOX™ is validated through a multi-centre clinical study, received regulatory approval in 2014, and has been used in medical practice in Switzerland since 2015). Specificity of 92.2%, sensitivity of 78.1% (Ciarloni et al., 2016).

- SelectMdx (MDxHealth, Belgium) – designed for prostate cancer detection. Measures the expression of two mRNA cancer-related biomarkers combined with clinical risk factors to stratify patients for clinically significant prostate cancer from a urine sample.

Tumor exosome detection liquid biopsy tests

- ExoDx Prostate IntelliScore (EPI) (Exosome diagnostics, USA) – a non-invasive exosome-based liquid biopsy, which quantifies three RNA targets in urine exosomes. The EPI test identifies patients at risk of high-grade prostate cancer. The test is carried out without the need for a digital rectal exam or a prostate massage and is independent of clinical variables. The main difference between the EPI assay and other assays such as SelectMDx which predict high-grade cancer, is the absence of clinical variables in the EPI algorithm. From the pooled analysis of three studies the combined cohort (n = 1212) gave an AUC of 0.70, with a sensitivity of 92.3%, specificity 30.1%, positive predictive value 36.4% and a negative predictive value of 90.1% (Margolis et al., 2022).

Antibody detection liquid biopsy tests

- Nodify CDT (Biodesix, USA) – doesn't directly detect cancer cells or mutations in DNA. It detects a panel of seven autoantibodies associated with lung cancer. These are proteins produced by the immune system that mistakenly target the body's own tissues. In the case of Nodify CDT, the autoantibodies are directed against antigens (proteins) associated with lung cancer. The specific identities of the seven autoantibodies within the Nodify CDT test are considered proprietary information by Biodesix. However, it is known they target lung cancer-associated antigens. By measuring the presence and levels of these autoantibodies, the Nodify CDT test helps to assess an individual's risk of lung cancer. It's typically used for patients with intermediate risk (5-65% based on physician assessment or scoring systems) detected through imaging techniques like lung nodules. It identifies the immune system's response to potential cancer by measuring autoantibodies with specificity of 98% and sensitivity of 28% (Healey et al., 2017).

Comparison of long-read sequencing technologies for cancer screening

Single molecule, real time sequencing by Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) and nanopore sequencing by Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) have been evaluated in several studies. It was determined by Yu et al. (2023) that both platforms show biases to sequence longer (1500 bp vs 200 bp) DNA fragments, with PacBio showing a stronger bias – 5-fold overrepresentation of long fragments vs 2-fold in ONT. Percentages of cfDNA fragments larger than 500 bp were around 6-fold higher in PacBio compared with ONT. End motif

profiles of cfDNA from PacBio and ONT were similar, yet exhibited platform-dependent patterns. Tissue-of-origin analysis based on single-molecule methylation patterns showed comparable performance on both platforms. Single molecule, real time sequencing (PacBio) generated data with higher percentages of long cfDNA compared with nanopore sequencing. Yet, a higher number of long cfDNA fragments eligible for the tissue-of-origin analysis could be obtained from nanopore sequencing due to its much higher throughput.

Decision support systems in oncology

Decision support systems (DSSs) are advanced systems that process large volumes of medical data, integrating evidence-based guidelines, risk assessment models, expertise and knowledge to facilitate more effective clinical decision-making. DSS can assist healthcare professionals in various aspects of care, including diagnosing diseases, determining appropriate treatment modalities, predicting patient outcomes, and ensuring compliance with best practices. A DSS in oncology is a computer-based tool designed to assist healthcare professionals in making informed decisions related to cancer risk, detection, diagnosis, and treatment (Suwanvecho et al., 2021; Walsh et al., 2019; Pawloski et al., 2019).

Artificial intelligence plays a crucial role in these systems to create predictive models based on patient's medical records and guidelines (Wang et al., 2023). These systems can continuously learn and interpret patient data, generating an alert level associated with the patient's risk of developing cancer.

DSS has enormous potential to enhance diagnostic accuracy and improve patient outcomes. By providing healthcare professionals with accurate and timely information, DSS can improve diagnostic accuracy and reduce the risk of misdiagnosis. This, in turn, can lead to better patient outcomes and increased patient satisfaction. For example, the DSS can greatly reduce the time doctors spend consulting relevant literature, enhancing their ability to provide accurate prevention, diagnoses and treatment recommendations more efficiently. Additionally, it can save patients the time and effort of traveling to top-tier hospitals, enabling them to access optimal treatment more promptly.

Characteristics of the DSS

Based on the working principle, DSS has several characteristics.

- **Improved diagnostic accuracy.** DSS can analyse patient data and synthesize relevant information, offering tailored treatment suggestions that help healthcare providers make more informed decisions about diagnoses and treatment plans.
- **Reduced medical errors.** By providing alerts for potential medication interactions, allergies, or contraindications, DSS can help prevent medical errors and enhance patient safety.
- **Enhanced decision-making.** DSS can reduce cognitive overload and human error by assisting healthcare providers in analysing complex patient data, synthesizing relevant information, and offering tailored treatment suggestions.
- **Cost savings.** DSS can help healthcare providers reduce healthcare costs by identifying unnecessary tests, avoiding duplicate procedures, and preventing complications that can result from medical errors.
- **Increased efficiency.** DSS can save time for healthcare providers by providing quick access to relevant information and automating certain processes, allowing them to focus on more critical aspects of patient care.

- **Scalability.** DSS can be implemented across various healthcare settings, from large hospitals to small clinics, allowing healthcare providers of all sizes to benefit from improved decision-making.

Key components typically involved in a DSS for breast cancer

1. **Risk assessment models.** DSS often incorporates risk assessment models that estimate a woman's likelihood of developing breast cancer based on factors such as age, family history, genetic mutations (e.g., *BRCA1/BRCA2*), reproductive history, and lifestyle factors (Casal-Guisande et al., 2022). Examples of commonly used risk assessment models include the Gail model, Tyrer-Cuzick model, and Breast Cancer Surveillance Consortium risk calculator.
2. **Imaging guidelines.** DSS provides guidance on breast cancer screening modalities, such as mammography, ultrasound, magnetic resonance imaging, and tomosynthesis, based on individual risk factors and screening recommendations.
3. **Screening schedules.** DSS generates personalized screening schedules based on a woman's age, risk profile, and screening history. It may recommend the frequency and timing of screening mammograms, along with the appropriate intervals for clinical breast exams and other imaging modalities.
4. **Diagnostic recommendations.** In cases where abnormalities are detected on screening exams or a woman presents with symptoms suggestive of breast cancer, DSS assists healthcare providers in determining the need for additional diagnostic tests, such as breast biopsy, fine-needle aspiration, or breast MRI, based on the likelihood of malignancy and patient preferences.
5. **Treatment decision support.** For women diagnosed with breast cancer, DSS provides decision support regarding treatment options, including surgery (e.g., lumpectomy or mastectomy), radiation therapy, chemotherapy, hormone therapy, targeted therapy, and immunotherapy. It may offer insights into the expected outcomes, risks, and benefits associated with each treatment modality, helping patients and clinicians make informed decisions (Mazo et al., 2020).
6. **Follow-up care.** DSS facilitates long-term monitoring and follow-up care for breast cancer survivors, including recommendations for surveillance imaging, laboratory tests, clinical evaluations, and lifestyle modifications to reduce the risk of cancer recurrence and promote overall health and well-being.

Risk assessment models for breast cancer

Gail model

The Gail risk assessment model (NIH, accessed 12-2024; Gail et al., 1989) is used for estimating the risk of developing breast cancer based on various factors, including age, age at first menstrual period, age at the time of the birth of a first child, family history of breast cancer, number of past breast biopsies, number of breast biopsies showing atypical hyperplasia, and race. This model calculates a woman's risk of developing breast cancer over the next 5 years and within her lifetime (up to age 90).

Tyrer-Cuzick model

The Tyrer-Cuzick risk assessment model (MagView, accessed 12-2024; Tyrer et al., 2004) is a tool used to estimate a woman's likelihood of developing breast cancer. It assesses a woman's 10-year and lifetime risk of developing breast cancer. The model considers factors such as age, height and weight, breast density, history and results of breast biopsies, personal history of breast or ovarian cancer, family history of breast or ovarian cancer, history of hormone use, Ashkenazi Jewish heritage, age at first menstrual period, age at first birth, age at menopause, and age at cancer diagnosis, if applicable. Based on the Tyrer-Cuzick score, a woman's risk of developing breast cancer is categorized as average, intermediate, or high.

Breast Cancer Surveillance Consortium (BCSC) risk calculator

The BCSC risk calculator (BCSC, accessed 12-2024) is a tool to estimate a woman's five-year risk of developing invasive breast cancer. It is based on various factors, including age, race/ethnicity, family history of breast or ovarian cancer, breast density, history of breast biopsies, and other risk factors. It can guide decisions on primary prevention, screening frequency, and supplemental imaging.

Examples of DSSs and risk calculators

DSSs in cancer care and treatment are widely used and gradually popularized all over the world. The most well-known are listed below:

- IBM Watson for Oncology (Somashkhar et al., 2018) provides evidence-informed therapeutic options for individual cancer patients by incorporating National Comprehensive Cancer Network guidelines and analysing evidence from published literature.
- CancerLinQ (Rubinstein et al., 2018) is a system that collects and organizes real-world data from various sources within the United States to support individuals involved in cancer care and treatment.
- OncoAnalytics (Dutton, 2017) provides information to clinicians on drugs, costs of care, and billing to improve the delivery of cancer care to patients.
- Tempus (Kwon, 2017) facilitates precision medicine approaches through its library of clinical and molecular data that clinicians can utilize for decision-making in oncology.

In addition, a list of risk assessment tools used in oncology are provided below:

- Cancer Risk Calculator (<https://cancer-risk-calculator.org/>)
- Hereditary Cancer Risk Tool (<https://ovarian.org.uk/risk/>)
- Breast Cancer Risk Assessment Tool (<https://bcrisktool.cancer.gov/calculator.html>)
- Invasive Breast Cancer Risk Calculator (<https://tools.bcsc-scc.ucdavis.edu/BC5yearRisk/#calculator>)

- Qcancer (<https://www.qcancer.org/>)
- Your Disease Risk (<https://siteman.wustl.edu/prevention/ydr/>)
- Prostate Cancer Risk Calculator
(<https://www.prostatecancer-riskcalculator.com/assess-your-risk-of-prostate-cancer>)
- Colorectal Cancer Risk Assessment Tool (<https://ccrisktool.cancer.gov/>)
- Lung Cancer Risk Estimation in Current and Past Smokers
(<https://www.msmanuals.com/professional/multimedia/clinical-calculator/lung-cancer-risk-estimation-in-current-and-past-smokers-6-year>)

And a list of risk calculators that consider PRS/pathogenic mutations:

- ASK2ME (<https://ask2me.org/calculator.php>)
- CanRisk (<https://www.canrisk.org/>)
- Antegenes (<https://antegenes.com/services/>)
- Prediction of DNA mismatch repair gene mutation status in incident colorectal cancer cases (<https://webapps.igc.ed.ac.uk/world/research/hnpccpredict/>)
- Lynch syndrome prediction model (<https://premm.dfci.harvard.edu/>)

Usage and future developments of the DSS

The storage capacity of an AI-based DSS far surpasses that of the human brain. It can rapidly collect, organize, and analyse stored information to generate accurate conclusions more quickly than humans, as demonstrated in areas such as diagnostic radiology and pathological imaging systems. However, significant advancements are required for DSS to fully integrate into real-world medical environments. Patient medical data needs to be standardized and shared on a national scale, and follow-up systems must be improved to gather complete patient information. Furthermore, countries should establish dedicated medical data warehouses to support DSS research. These data repositories should align with international guidelines and the unique medical systems of different countries to maximize the DSS's potential in serving patients globally (Kux et al., 2017).

It is important to emphasize that DSS technology cannot currently replace oncologists (Suwanvecho et al., 2021). Instead, it should be regarded as a valuable assistant or mentor for doctors. For example, DSS applications in cervical cancer prevention have demonstrated remarkable progress, with recommendation accuracy reaching 93% based on the American Society of Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology guidelines (Ravikumar et al., 2018). Nevertheless, some physicians might mistakenly believe that DSS will eventually replace them. However, studies show that only 60% of treatment recommendations for breast, lung, colon, and rectal cancers are identical or equally acceptable, and 70% of DSS therapeutic options are identical or acceptable. Also, it is essential to recognize that medicine is not purely a scientific discipline – it also encompasses social and psychological

dimensions. Physicians must account for these factors and tailor individualized approach for each patient.

Benefits of cancer DSSs

Cancer DSS tools are designed to assist doctors in making informed decisions about whether to refer patients or request additional diagnostic investigations when there is a potential risk of cancer. These tools estimate the likelihood of a patient having a specific type of cancer. The risk assessment is based on a combination of factors, including symptoms, medical history, genetic data, and demographic information. By integrating data from the patient's health records along with real-time inputs during appointments, the tool provides an evidence-based assessment of cancer risk and encourages the oncologist to explore the situation further and consider referring the patient for screening or additional tests if necessary.

For example, **using data from national biobanks, a DSS could be used to classify people with a high polygenic risk for cancer to a group who would be offered the LB based next generation sequencing analysis as a refinement test.** It is not feasible to perform the methylation analysis across the population. Rather, it should only be offered to people with very high PRS, e.g. top 1%. This allows for starting intervention before conventional cancer analysis methods which should improve the prevention and treatment outcomes. Additional value of this approach is that in addition to cancer PRS, each person's microarray data can be used for producing PRS data for many other common and complex diseases and even for pharmacogenomics.

Main achievements

This report conducted an extensive literature review, delving into liquid biopsy techniques and decision support systems for cancer detection and prevention. It provided a comprehensive examination of state-of-the-art methodologies, detailing relevant recommendations and identifying critical challenges. By highlighting key aspects of liquid biopsy, including polygenic risk scores and advanced decision support tools, the report lays a foundation for leveraging cutting-edge technologies to enhance early cancer detection and intervention strategies.

Impact

This report provides key insights and challenges to leverage the use of liquid biopsies with polygenic risk scores and decision support systems with the ultimate goal of establishing population-based early clinical intervention programs for cancer prevention and monitoring. The insights provided in this report hold transformative potential for healthcare at both European and global levels. By integrating liquid biopsies, polygenic risk assessments, and decision support systems into routine clinical workflows, the findings aim to revolutionize cancer prevention and monitoring. The proposed approaches could optimize resource allocation, support targeted interventions, and reduce healthcare burdens through earlier diagnosis and personalized care, ultimately improving patient outcomes and survival rates.

References

- Adashek, J. J., Janku, F., & Kurzrock, R. (2021). Signed in Blood: Circulating Tumor DNA in Cancer Diagnosis, Treatment and Screening. *Cancers*, 13(14), 3600. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers13143600>
- Aggarwal, C., Marmarelis, M. E., Hwang, W.-T., Scholes, D. G., McWilliams, T. L., Singh, A. P., Sun, L., Kosteva, J., Costello, M. R., Cohen, R. B., Langer, C. J., Doucette, A., Gabriel, P. N., Shulman, L. N., Rendle, K. A., Thompson, J. C., Bekelman, J. E., & Carpenter, E. L. (2023). Association Between Availability of Molecular Genotyping Results and Overall Survival in Patients With Advanced Nonsquamous Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer. *JCO Precision Oncology*, 7, e2300191. <https://doi.org/10.1200/PO.23.00191>
- Alese, O. B., Cook, N., Ortega-Franco, A., Ulanja, M. B., Tan, L., & Tie, J. (2022). Circulating Tumor DNA: An Emerging Tool in Gastrointestinal Cancers. *American Society of Clinical Oncology Educational Book. American Society of Clinical Oncology. Annual Meeting*, 42, 1–20. https://doi.org/10.1200/EDBK_349143
- Alix-Panabières, C., & Pantel, K. (2021). Liquid Biopsy: From Discovery to Clinical Application. *Cancer Discovery*, 11(4), 858–873. <https://doi.org/10.1158/2159-8290.CD-20-1311>
- Anand, P., Kunnumakkara, A. B., Sundaram, C., Harikumar, K. B., Tharakan, S. T., Lai, O. S., Sung, B., & Aggarwal, B. B. (2008). Cancer is a preventable disease that requires major lifestyle changes. *Pharmaceutical Research*, 25(9), 2097–2116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11095-008-9661-9>
- Anfossi, S., Babayan, A., Pantel, K., & Calin, G. A. (2018). Clinical utility of circulating non-coding RNAs—An update. *Nature Reviews. Clinical Oncology*, 15(9), 541–563. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41571-018-0035-x>
- Aziz, Z., Wagner, S., Agyekum, A., Pumpalova, Y. S., Prest, M., Lim, F., Rustgi, S., Kastrinos, F., Grady, W. M., & Hur, C. (2023). Cost-Effectiveness of Liquid Biopsy for Colorectal Cancer Screening in Patients Who Are Unscreened. *JAMA Network Open*, 6(11), e2343392. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2023.43392>
- Batool, S. M., Yekula, A., Khanna, P., Hsia, T., Gamblin, A. S., Ekanayake, E., Escobedo, A. K., You, D. G., Castro, C. M., Im, H., Kilic, T., Garlin, M. A., Skog, J., Dinulescu, D. M., Dudley, J., Agrawal, N., Cheng, J., Abtin, F., Aberle, D. R., ... Balaj, L. (2023). The Liquid Biopsy Consortium: Challenges and opportunities for early cancer detection and monitoring. *Cell Reports. Medicine*, 4(10), 101198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xcrm.2023.101198>
- BCSC. Retrieved December 28, 2024, from <https://www.bpsc-research.org/tools>
- Bonstingl, L., Skofler, C., Ulz, C., Zinnegger, M., Sallinger, K., Schönberger, J., Schuch, K., Pankratz, K., Borrás-Cherrier, A., Somodi, V., Abuja, P. M., Oberauner-Wappis, L., Bauernhofer, T., Kroneis, T., & El-Heliebi, A. (2023). Clinical application of ISO and CEN/TS standards for liquid biopsies—Information everybody wants but nobody wants to pay for (p. 2023.12.04.23299422). *medRxiv*. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.12.04.23299422>
- Brockley, L. J., Souza, V. G. P., Forder, A., Pewarchuk, M. E., Erkan, M., Telkar, N., Benard, K., Trejo, J., Stewart, M. D., Stewart, G. L., Reis, P. P., Lam, W. L., & Martinez, V. D. (2023). Sequence-Based Platforms for Discovering Biomarkers in Liquid Biopsy of Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer. *Cancers*, 15(8), 2275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers15082275>
- Caputo, V., Ciardiello, F., Corte, C. M. D., Martini, G., Troiani, T., & Napolitano, S. (2023). Diagnostic value of liquid biopsy in the era of precision medicine: 10 years of clinical

- evidence in cancer. *Exploration of Targeted Anti-Tumor Therapy*, 4(1), 102–138. <https://doi.org/10.37349/etat.2023.00125>
- Casal-Guisande, M., Comesaña-Campos, A., Dutra, I., Cerqueiro-Pequeño, J., & Bouza-Rodríguez, J.-B. (2022). Design and Development of an Intelligent Clinical Decision Support System Applied to the Evaluation of Breast Cancer Risk. *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, 12(2), 169. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm12020169>
- CELLSEARCH®. Retrieved December 28, 2024, from <https://www.cellsearchctc.com/>
- Chen, M., & Zhao, H. (2019). Next-generation sequencing in liquid biopsy: Cancer screening and early detection. *Human Genomics*, 13(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40246-019-0220-8>
- Chen, X., Gole, J., Gore, A., He, Q., Lu, M., Min, J., Yuan, Z., Yang, X., Jiang, Y., Zhang, T., Suo, C., Li, X., Cheng, L., Zhang, Z., Niu, H., Li, Z., Xie, Z., Shi, H., Zhang, X., ... Jin, L. (2020). Non-invasive early detection of cancer four years before conventional diagnosis using a blood test. *Nature Communications*, 11(1), 3475. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-17316-z>
- Cheng, C., Omura-Minamisawa, M., Kang, Y., Hara, T., Koike, I., & Inoue, T. (2009). Quantification of circulating cell-free DNA in the plasma of cancer patients during radiation therapy. *Cancer Science*, 100(2), 303–309. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1349-7006.2008.01021.x>
- Choi, E.-J., & Kim, Y.-J. (2022). Liquid biopsy for early detection and therapeutic monitoring of hepatocellular carcinoma. *Journal of Liver Cancer*, 22(2), 103–114. <https://doi.org/10.17998/jlc.2022.09.08>
- Chung, D. C., Gray, D. M., Singh, H., Issaka, R. B., Raymond, V. M., Eagle, C., Hu, S., Chudova, D. I., Talasz, A., Greenson, J. K., Sinicrope, F. A., Gupta, S., & Grady, W. M. (2024). A Cell-free DNA Blood-Based Test for Colorectal Cancer Screening. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 390(11), 973–983. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2304714>
- Ciarloni, L., Ehrensberger, S. H., Imaizumi, N., Monnier-Benoit, S., Nichita, C., Myung, S.-J., Kim, J. S., Song, S. Y., Kim, T. I., van der Weg, B., Meier, R., Borovicka, J., Beglinger, C., Vallet, C., Maerten, P., Rüegg, C., & Dorta, G. (2016). Development and Clinical Validation of a Blood Test Based on 29-Gene Expression for Early Detection of Colorectal Cancer. *Clinical Cancer Research: An Official Journal of the American Association for Cancer Research*, 22(18), 4604–4611. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-15-2057>
- Cohen, J. D., Li, L., Wang, Y., Thoburn, C., Afsari, B., Danilova, L., Douville, C., Javed, A. A., Wong, F., Mattox, A., Hruban, R. H., Wolfgang, C. L., Goggins, M. G., Dal Molin, M., Wang, T.-L., Roden, R., Klein, A. P., Ptak, J., Dobbyn, L., ... Papadopoulos, N. (2018). Detection and localization of surgically resectable cancers with a multi-analyte blood test. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 359(6378), 926–930. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aar3247>
- COLOX - Novigenix. Retrieved June 3, 2024, from <https://novigenix.com/colox-solution/>
- Connal, S., Cameron, J. M., Sala, A., Brennan, P. M., Palmer, D. S., Palmer, J. D., Perlow, H., & Baker, M. J. (2023). Liquid biopsies: The future of cancer early detection. *Journal of Translational Medicine*, 21(1), 118. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12967-023-03960-8>
- Connors, D., Allen, J., Alvarez, J. D., Boyle, J., Cristofanilli, M., Hiller, C., Keating, S., Kelloff, G., Leiman, L., McCormack, R., Merino, D., Morgan, E., Pantel, K., Rolfo, C., Serrano, M. J., Pia Sanzone, A., Schlange, T., Sigman, C., & Stewart, M. (2020). International liquid biopsy standardization alliance white paper. *Critical Reviews in Oncology/Hematology*, 156, 103112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.critrevonc.2020.103112>

- Cui, W., Milner-Watts, C., O'Sullivan, H., Lyons, H., Minchom, A., Bhosle, J., Davidson, M., Yousaf, N., Scott, S., Faull, I., Kushnir, M., Nagy, R., O'Brien, M., & Papat, S. (2022). Up-front cell-free DNA next generation sequencing improves target identification in UK first line advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) patients. *European Journal of Cancer (Oxford, England: 1990)*, 171, 44–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2022.05.012>
- De Rubis, G., Rajeev Krishnan, S., & Bebawy, M. (2019). Liquid Biopsies in Cancer Diagnosis, Monitoring, and Prognosis. *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, 40(3), 172–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tips.2019.01.006>
- Diehl, F., Schmidt, K., Choti, M. A., Romans, K., Goodman, S., Li, M., Thornton, K., Agrawal, N., Sokoll, L., Szabo, S. A., Kinzler, K. W., Vogelstein, B., & Diaz, L. A. (2008). Circulating mutant DNA to assess tumor dynamics. *Nature Medicine*, 14(9), 985–990. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.1789>
- Domínguez-Vigil, I. G., Moreno-Martínez, A. K., Wang, J. Y., Roehrl, M. H. A., & Barrera-Saldaña, H. A. (2018). The dawn of the liquid biopsy in the fight against cancer. *Oncotarget*, 9(2), 2912–2922. <https://doi.org/10.18632/oncotarget.23131>
- Drokow, E. K., Sun, K., Ahmed, H. A. W., Akpabla, G. S., Song, J., & Shi, M. (2019). Circulating microRNA as diagnostic biomarkers for haematological cancers: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Cancer Management and Research*, 11, 4313–4326. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CMAR.S199126>
- Dutton, G. (2017). Making Every Cancer Care Outcome Count. *Genetic Engineering & Biotechnology News*, 37(4), 6–7. <https://doi.org/10.1089/gen.37.04.04>
- Fagery, M., Khorshidi, H. A., Wong, S. Q., Vu, M., & IJzerman, M. (2023). Health Economic Evidence and Modeling Challenges for Liquid Biopsy Assays in Cancer Management: A Systematic Literature Review. *Pharmacoeconomics*, 47(10), 1229–1248. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40273-023-01292-5>
- Fernandez, A. F., Assenov, Y., Martin-Subero, J. I., Balint, B., Siebert, R., Taniguchi, H., Yamamoto, H., Hidalgo, M., Tan, A.-C., Galm, O., Ferrer, I., Sanchez-Cespedes, M., Villanueva, A., Carmona, J., Sanchez-Mut, J. V., Berdasco, M., Moreno, V., Capella, G., Monk, D., ... Esteller, M. (2012). A DNA methylation fingerprint of 1628 human samples. *Genome Research*, 22(2), 407–419. <https://doi.org/10.1101/gr.119867.110>
- Finotti, A., Allegretti, M., Gasparello, J., Giacomini, P., Spandidos, D. A., Spoto, G., & Gambari, R. (2018). Liquid biopsy and PCR-free ultrasensitive detection systems in oncology (Review). *International Journal of Oncology*, 53(4), 1395–1434. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijo.2018.4516>
- Gail, M. H., Brinton, L. A., Byar, D. P., Corle, D. K., Green, S. B., Schairer, C., & Mulvihill, J. J. (1989). Projecting Individualized Probabilities of Developing Breast Cancer for White Females Who Are Being Examined Annually. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 81(24), 1879–1886. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/81.24.1879>
- Haese, A., Trooskens, G., Steyaert, S., Hessels, D., Brawer, M., Vlaeminck-Guillem, V., Ruffion, A., Tilki, D., Schalken, J., Groskopf, J., & Van Criekinge, W. (2019). Multicenter Optimization and Validation of a 2-Gene mRNA Urine Test for Detection of Clinically Significant Prostate Cancer before Initial Prostate Biopsy. *The Journal of Urology*, 202(2), 256–263. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JU.0000000000000293>
- Hanin, L. (2023). The circulation stage of the metastatic cascade: A mathematical description and its clinical implications. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 572, 111582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtbi.2023.111582>

- Healey, G. F., Macdonald, I. K., Reynolds, C., Allen, J., & Murray, A. (2017). Tumor-Associated Autoantibodies: Re-Optimization of EarlyCDT-Lung Diagnostic Performance and Its Application to Indeterminate Pulmonary Nodules. *Journal of Cancer Therapy*, 8(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jct.2017.85043>
- Hubbell, E., Clarke, C. A., Aravanis, A. M., & Berg, C. D. (2021). Modeled Reductions in Late-stage Cancer with a Multi-Cancer Early Detection Test. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention: A Publication of the American Association for Cancer Research, Cosponsored by the American Society of Preventive Oncology*, 30(3), 460–468. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-20-1134>
- IJzerman, M. J., de Boer, J., Azad, A., Degeling, K., Geoghegan, J., Hewitt, C., Holland, F., Lee, B., To, Y. H., Tothill, R. W., Wright, G., Tie, J., & Dawson, S.-J. (2021). Towards Routine Implementation of Liquid Biopsies in Cancer Management: It Is Always Too Early, until Suddenly It Is Too Late. *Diagnostics (Basel, Switzerland)*, 11(1), 103. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics11010103>
- Klein, E. A., Richards, D., Cohn, A., Tummala, M., Lapham, R., Cosgrove, D., Chung, G., Clement, J., Gao, J., Hunkapiller, N., Jamshidi, A., Kurtzman, K. N., Seiden, M. V., Swanton, C., & Liu, M. C. (2021). Clinical validation of a targeted methylation-based multi-cancer early detection test using an independent validation set. *Annals of Oncology: Official Journal of the European Society for Medical Oncology*, 32(9), 1167–1177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annonc.2021.05.806>
- Kux, B. R., Majeed, R. W., Ahlbrandt, J., & Röhrig, R. (2017). Factors Influencing the Implementation and Distribution of Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS). *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics*, 243, 127–131.
- Kwon, D. (2017). Tempus and Mayo Clinic Partner for Data-Driven Cancer Care. *Clinical OMICs*, 4(1), 14–14. <https://doi.org/10.1089/clinomi.04.01.15>
- Kwon, H.-J., Shin, S. H., Kim, H. H., Min, N. Y., Lim, Y., Joo, T.-W., Lee, K. J., Jeong, M.-S., Kim, H., Yun, S.-Y., Kim, Y., Park, D., Joo, J., Bae, J.-S., Lee, S., Jeong, B.-H., Lee, K., Lee, H., Kim, H. K., ... Lee, M. S. (2023). Advances in methylation analysis of liquid biopsy in early cancer detection of colorectal and lung cancer. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 13502. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-40611-w>
- Leung, F., Kulasingam, V., Diamandis, E. P., Hoon, D. S. B., Kinzler, K., Pantel, K., & Alix-Panabières, C. (2016). Circulating Tumor DNA as a Cancer Biomarker: Fact or Fiction? *Clinical Chemistry*, 62(8), 1054–1060. <https://doi.org/10.1373/clinchem.2016.260331>
- Liquid Biopsy In Oncology: An Increasingly Crowded Landscape. (2016, September 6). *Insights*. <https://insights.citeline.com//MT103794/Liquid-Biopsy-In-Oncology-An-Increasingly-Crowded-Landscape/>
- Lone, S. N., Nisar, S., Masoodi, T., Singh, M., Rizwan, A., Hashem, S., El-Rifai, W., Bedognetti, D., Batra, S. K., Haris, M., Bhat, A. A., & Macha, M. A. (2022). Liquid biopsy: A step closer to transform diagnosis, prognosis and future of cancer treatments. *Molecular Cancer*, 21(1), 79. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-022-01543-7>
- MagView. Tyrer-Cuzick Risk Calculator for Breast Cancer Risk Assessment. Retrieved December 28, 2024, from <https://ibis-risk-calculator.magview.com/>
- Mariotto, A. B., Enewold, L., Zhao, J., Zeruto, C. A., & Yabroff, K. R. (2020). Medical Care Costs Associated with Cancer Survivorship in the United States. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention: A Publication of the American Association for Cancer Research, Cosponsored by the American Society of Preventive Oncology*, 29(7), 1304–1312. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-19-1534>

- Margolis, E., Brown, G., Partin, A., Carter, B., McKiernan, J., Tutrone, R., Torkler, P., Fischer, C., Tadigotla, V., Noerholm, M., Donovan, M. J., & Skog, J. (2022). Predicting high-grade prostate cancer at initial biopsy: Clinical performance of the ExoDx (EPI) Prostate Intelliscore test in three independent prospective studies. *Prostate Cancer and Prostatic Diseases*, 25(2), 296–301. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41391-021-00456-8>
- Markus, H., Chandrananda, D., Moore, E., Mouliere, F., Morris, J., Brenton, J. D., Smith, C. G., & Rosenfeld, N. (2022). Refined characterization of circulating tumor DNA through biological feature integration. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 1928. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-05606-z>
- Martins, I., Ribeiro, I. P., Jorge, J., Gonçalves, A. C., Sarmiento-Ribeiro, A. B., Melo, J. B., & Carreira, I. M. (2021). Liquid Biopsies: Applications for Cancer Diagnosis and Monitoring. *Genes*, 12(3), 349. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12030349>
- Mazo, C., Kearns, C., Mooney, C., & Gallagher, W. M. (2020). Clinical Decision Support Systems in Breast Cancer: A Systematic Review. *Cancers*, 12(2), 369. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers12020369>
- Mouliere, F., Chandrananda, D., Piskorz, A. M., Moore, E. K., Morris, J., Ahlborn, L. B., Mair, R., Goranova, T., Marass, F., Heider, K., Wan, J. C. M., Supernat, A., Hudecova, I., Gounaris, I., Ros, S., Jimenez-Linan, M., Garcia-Corbacho, J., Patel, K., Østrup, O., ... Rosenfeld, N. (2018). Enhanced detection of circulating tumor DNA by fragment size analysis. *Science Translational Medicine*, 10(466), eaat4921. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.aat4921>
- Nassiri, F., Chakravarthy, A., Feng, S., Shen, S. Y., Nejad, R., Zuccato, J. A., Voisin, M. R., Patil, V., Horbinski, C., Aldape, K., Zadeh, G., & De Carvalho, D. D. (2020). Detection and discrimination of intracranial tumors using plasma cell-free DNA methylomes. *Nature Medicine*, 26(7), 1044–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0932-2>
- NIH. Breast Cancer Risk Assessment Tool: Online Calculator (The Gail Model). Retrieved December 28, 2024, from <https://bcrisktool.cancer.gov>
- Olmedillas-López, S., Olivera-Salazar, R., García-Arranz, M., & García-Olmo, D. (2022). Current and Emerging Applications of Droplet Digital PCR in Oncology: An Updated Review. *Molecular Diagnosis & Therapy*, 26(1), 61–87. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40291-021-00562-2>
- PacBio. Revio. Retrieved June 2, 2024, from <https://www.pacb.com/revio/>
- Pawloski, P. A., Brooks, G. A., Nielsen, M. E., & Olson-Bullis, B. A. (2019). A Systematic Review of Clinical Decision Support Systems for Clinical Oncology Practice. *Journal of the National Comprehensive Cancer Network: JNCCN*, 17(4), 331–338. <https://doi.org/10.6004/jnccn.2018.7104>
- Peng, X., Li, H.-D., Wu, F.-X., & Wang, J. (2021). Identifying the tissues-of-origin of circulating cell-free DNAs is a promising way in noninvasive diagnostics. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 22(3), bbaa060. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbaa060>
- Ramirez-Garrastacho, M., Bajo-Santos, C., Line, A., Martens-Uzunova, E. S., de la Fuente, J. M., Moros, M., Soekmadji, C., Tasken, K. A., & Llorente, A. (2022). Extracellular vesicles as a source of prostate cancer biomarkers in liquid biopsies: A decade of research. *British Journal of Cancer*, 126(3), 331–350. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41416-021-01610-8>
- Rashkin, S. R., Graff, R. E., Kachuri, L., Thai, K. K., Alexeeff, S. E., Blatchins, M. A., Cavazos, T. B., Corley, D. A., Emami, N. C., Hoffman, J. D., Jorgenson, E., Kushi, L. H., Meyers, T. J., Van Den Eeden, S. K., Ziv, E., Habel, L. A., Hoffmann, T. J., Sakoda, L. C., & Witte, J. S. (2020). Pan-cancer study detects genetic risk variants and shared genetic basis in two

- large cohorts. *Nature Communications*, 11, 4423. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18246-6>
- Ravikumar, K. E., MacLaughlin, K. L., Scheitel, M. R., Kessler, M., Waghlikar, K. B., Liu, H., & Chaudhry, R. (2018). Improving the Accuracy of a Clinical Decision Support System for Cervical Cancer Screening and Surveillance. *Applied Clinical Informatics*, 9(1), 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0037-1617451>
- Razavi, P., Li, B. T., Brown, D. N., Jung, B., Hubbell, E., Shen, R., Abida, W., Juluru, K., De Bruijn, I., Hou, C., Venn, O., Lim, R., Anand, A., Maddala, T., Gnerre, S., Vijaya Satya, R., Liu, Q., Shen, L., Eattock, N., ... Reis-Filho, J. S. (2019). High-intensity sequencing reveals the sources of plasma circulating cell-free DNA variants. *Nature Medicine*, 25(12), 1928–1937. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-019-0652-7>
- Roadmap Epigenomics Consortium, Kundaje, A., Meuleman, W., Ernst, J., Bilenky, M., Yen, A., Heravi-Moussavi, A., Kheradpour, P., Zhang, Z., Wang, J., Ziller, M. J., Amin, V., Whitaker, J. W., Schultz, M. D., Ward, L. D., Sarkar, A., Quon, G., Sandstrom, R. S., Eaton, M. L., ... Kellis, M. (2015). Integrative analysis of 111 reference human epigenomes. *Nature*, 518(7539), 317–330. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14248>
- Rubinstein, S. M., & Warner, J. L. (2018). CancerLinQ: Origins, Implementation, and Future Directions. *JCO Clinical Cancer Informatics*, 2, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1200/CCI.17.00060>
- Sala, A., Cameron, J. M., Jenkins, C. A., Barr, H., Christie, L., Conn, J. J. A., Evans, T. R. J., Harris, D. A., Palmer, D. S., Rinaldi, C., Theakstone, A. G., & Baker, M. J. (2022). Liquid Biopsy for Pancreatic Cancer Detection Using Infrared Spectroscopy. *Cancers*, 14(13), 3048. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14133048>
- Sánchez-Herrero, E., Serna-Blasco, R., Robado de Lope, L., González-Rumayor, V., Romero, A., & Provencio, M. (2022). Circulating Tumor DNA as a Cancer Biomarker: An Overview of Biological Features and Factors That may Impact on ctDNA Analysis. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12, 943253. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2022.943253>
- Schramm, W., Hollenbenders, Y., & Kurscheidt, M. (2024). Explorative cost-effectiveness analysis of colorectal cancer recurrence detection with next-generation sequencing liquid biopsy in Spain, France, and Germany. *Therapeutic Advances in Gastroenterology*, 17, 17562848241248246. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17562848241248246>
- Shegekar, T., Vodithala, S., & Juganavar, A. (2023). The Emerging Role of Liquid Biopsies in Revolutionising Cancer Diagnosis and Therapy. *Cureus*, 15(8), e43650. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.43650>
- Somashekhar, S. P., Sepúlveda, M.-J., Puglielli, S., Norden, A. D., Shortliffe, E. H., Rohit Kumar, C., Rauthan, A., Arun Kumar, N., Patil, P., Rhee, K., & Ramya, Y. (2018). Watson for Oncology and breast cancer treatment recommendations: Agreement with an expert multidisciplinary tumor board. *Annals of Oncology*, 29(2), 418–423. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mdx781>
- Stejskal, P., Goodarzi, H., Srovnal, J., Hajdúch, M., van 't Veer, L. J., & Magbanua, M. J. M. (2023). Circulating tumor nucleic acids: Biology, release mechanisms, and clinical relevance. *Molecular Cancer*, 22(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-022-01710-w>
- Suwanvecho, S., Suwanrusme, H., Jirakulaporn, T., Issarachai, S., Taechakraichana, N., Lungchukiet, P., Decha, W., Boonpakdee, W., Thanakarn, N., Wongrattananon, P., Preininger, A. M., Solomon, M., Wang, S., Hekmat, R., Dankwa-Mullan, I., Shortliffe, E., Patel, V. L., Arriaga, Y., Jackson, G. P., & Kiatikajornthada, N. (2021). Comparison of an oncology clinical decision-support system's recommendations with actual treatment

- decisions. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 28(4), 832–838. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocaa334>
- Sysmex product details. (2024, June 2). <https://www.sysmex-europe.com/products/products-detail/plasma-seqsensei-breast-cancer-ivd-kit/>
- Tamura, T., Yoshioka, Y., Sakamoto, S., Ichikawa, T., & Ochiya, T. (2021). Extracellular vesicles as a promising biomarker resource in liquid biopsy for cancer. *Extracellular Vesicles and Circulating Nucleic Acids*, 2(2), 148–174. <https://doi.org/10.20517/evcna.2021.06>
- Theakstone, A. G., Brennan, P. M., Jenkinson, M. D., Mills, S. J., Syed, K., Rinaldi, C., Xu, Y., Goodacre, R., Butler, H. J., Palmer, D. S., Smith, B. R., & Baker, M. J. (2021). Rapid Spectroscopic Liquid Biopsy for the Universal Detection of Brain Tumours. *Cancers*, 13(15), 3851. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers13153851>
- Theakstone, A. G., Rinaldi, C., Butler, H. J., Cameron, J. M., Confield, L. R., Rutherford, S. H., Sala, A., Sangamnerkar, S., & Baker, M. J. (2021). Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy of biofluids: A practical approach. *Translational Biophotonics*, 3(2), e202000025. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tbio.202000025>
- Turnbull, C., Wald, N., Sullivan, R., Pharoah, P., Houlston, R. S., Aggarwal, A., Hogarth, S., & McCartney, M. (2024). GRAIL-Galleri: Why the special treatment? *The Lancet*, 403(10425), 431–432. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(23\)02830-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(23)02830-1)
- Tyrer, J., Duffy, S. W., & Cuzick, J. (2004). A breast cancer prediction model incorporating familial and personal risk factors. *Statistics in Medicine*, 23(7), 1111–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.1668>
- Walsh, S., de Jong, E. E. C., van Timmeren, J. E., Ibrahim, A., Compter, I., Peerlings, J., Sanduleanu, S., Refaee, T., Keek, S., Larue, R. T. H. M., van Wijk, Y., Even, A. J. G., Jochems, A., Barakat, M. S., Leijenaar, R. T. H., & Lambin, P. (2019). Decision Support Systems in Oncology. *JCO Clinical Cancer Informatics*, 3, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1200/CCI.18.00001>
- Wan, J. C. M., Massie, C., Garcia-Corbacho, J., Mouliere, F., Brenton, J. D., Caldas, C., Pacey, S., Baird, R., & Rosenfeld, N. (2017). Liquid biopsies come of age: Towards implementation of circulating tumour DNA. *Nature Reviews. Cancer*, 17(4), 223–238. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrc.2017.7>
- Wang, L., Chen, X., Zhang, L., Li, L., Huang, Y., Sun, Y., & Yuan, X. (2023). Artificial intelligence in clinical decision support systems for oncology. *International Journal of Medical Sciences*, 20(1), 79–86. <https://doi.org/10.7150/ijms.77205>
- Wu, T.-M., Liu, J.-B., Liu, Y., Shi, Y., Li, W., Wang, G.-R., Ma, Y.-S., & Fu, D. (2020). Power and Promise of Next-Generation Sequencing in Liquid Biopsies and Cancer Control. *Cancer Control: Journal of the Moffitt Cancer Center*, 27(3), 1073274820934805. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073274820934805>
- Wyatt, A. W., Annala, M., Aggarwal, R., Beja, K., Feng, F., Youngren, J., Foye, A., Lloyd, P., Nykter, M., Beer, T. M., Alumkal, J. J., Thomas, G. V., Reiter, R. E., Rettig, M. B., Evans, C. P., Gao, A. C., Chi, K. N., Small, E. J., & Gleave, M. E. (2017). Concordance of Circulating Tumor DNA and Matched Metastatic Tissue Biopsy in Prostate Cancer. *Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 109(12), djx118. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/djx118>
- Yan, Y., Guo, Q., Wang, F., Adhikari, R., Zhu, Z., Zhang, H., Zhou, W., Yu, H., Li, J., & Zhang, J. (2021). Cell-Free DNA: Hope and Potential Application in Cancer. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 9, 639233. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2021.639233>
- Zhang, L., Liang, Y., Li, S., Zeng, F., Meng, Y., Chen, Z., Liu, S., Tao, Y., & Yu, F. (2019). The interplay of circulating tumor DNA and chromatin modification, therapeutic resistance, and metastasis. *Molecular Cancer*, 18(1), 36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-019-0989-z>

Deliverable D5.2 - Inventory of the DSS and recommendations for establishing large scale population-based early intervention programs for the prevention of cancers utilizing NGS and LB - Version 1

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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